

Studies in the synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins: Part X*. Synthesis of 3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo (3,2-c) benzopyrones

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4-Hydroxy-3-benzoylcoumarin when condensed with ethyl bromo acetate gave ethyl-3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylate (IVa), which on hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation furnished 3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVc). 4-Hydroxy-6-methyl-3-benzoylcoumarin on similar series of reactions gave (IVf). (IIIb) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave (IIb).

The general feature of the compounds like warfarin (Ia), marcoumar (Ib), coumachlor (Ic) and sintron (Id) which possess anticoagulant property is that they have a phenyl ring separated from 4-hydroxycoumarin ring by one carbon atom at 3-position of coumarin ring system. Arora and Mathur¹ reported that α -methyl dioxophenylpyrano benzopyran (IIa) wherein phenyl ring is separated from 4-hydroxycoumarin ring by two carbon atoms, possesses anticoagulant activity comparable to that of dicoumarol. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise 3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran in which a phenyl ring is separated from the 4-hydroxycoumarin ring systems by one carbon atom and (IIb) to study their anticoagulant property.

- I. a. R = H, R₁ = CH₂COCH₃
 b. R = H, R₁ = C₂H₅
 c. R = Cl, R₁ = -CH₂COCH₃
 d. R = NO₂, R₁ = -CH₂COCH₃

- II. a. R = C₆H₅; R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = H
 b. R = H; R₁ = -C₆H₅; R₂ = -CH₃

- III. a. R = COC₆H₅; R₁ = H; R₂ = CH₃
 b. R = H; R₁ = COC₆H₅; R₂ = CH₃
 c. R = -CH₂COOC₂H₅; R₁ = -COC₆H₅;
 R₂ = H

- IV. a. R = -COOC₂H₅; R₁ = H
 b. R = COOH; R₁ = H
 c. R = R₁ = H
 d. R = -COOC₂H₅; R₁ = CH₃
 e. R = -COOH; R₁ = CH₃
 f. R = H; R₁ = CH₃

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1. R. B. Arora and C. N. Mathur, *Brit. J. Pharmac. Chemother.*, 1963, 20, 29.

When 4-hydroxy-3-benzoylcoumarin² was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate by refluxing them in acetone for 25 hrs, ethyl-3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylate (IVa) was obtained as the only isolable product. This indicated that the reaction went further involving the ring closure of ethyl-3-benzoyl-4-coumarinyl oxyacetate (IIIc). The ester (IVa) was hydrolysed to the acid (IVb) which was subsequently decarboxylated to give 3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo (3,2-c)benzopyran (IVc).

4-Hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin was benzoylated in the presence of pyridine and piperidine to give 4-benzoyloxy-6-methylcoumarin (IIIa) which on Fries migration afforded 3-benzoyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (IIIb). This on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave 4-phenyl-9-methyl-2,5-dioxo-2H,5H-pyrano (3,2-c)benzopyran (IIb). 3-Benzoyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (IIIb) was also condensed with ethyl bromoacetate in acetone to give ethyl-3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylate (IVd). This ester (IVd) was hydrolysed to 3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IVe) which was subsequently decarboxylated to yield 3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVf).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl-3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylate (IVa): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-3-benzoylcoumarin (2.0 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (2 ml.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 25 hrs. After the evaporation of acetone, water was added to the mixture. The separated product was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The residue crystallised from dil. alcohol, m.p. 162°. Yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 71.93; H, 3.77. $C_{20}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 71.85; H, 4.22%).

3-Phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IVb): Ethyl-3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylate (1 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (5 ml.) and refluxed with sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 20%) on a water bath for 45 mins. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and acidified. The separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution, acidified and finally crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 262°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 70.82; H, 3.28. $C_{18}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 70.59; H, 3.29%).

3-Phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVc): A mixture of 3-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (0.5 g.), copper bronze (0.4 g.) and quinoline (5 ml.) was heated on a sand bath for 1 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in dilute hydrochloric acid was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally crystallized from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 161°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 77.76; H, 3.78. $C_{17}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 77.85; H, 3.84%).

4-Benzoyloxy-6-methylcoumarin (IIIa): To a solution of 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (5.0 g.) in dry pyridine (40 ml.) and piperidine (1 ml.) benzoyl chloride (7.5 ml.) was slowly added at 0° with stirring. After the addition, the reaction mixture was kept for 5–10 mins

and then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from dil. alcohol, m.p. 131°. Yield 4.8 g. (Found: C, 72.61; H, 4.11. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.85; H, 4.32%).

Fries migration: 4-Hydroxy-3-benzoyl-6-methylcoumarin (IVh): A mixture of 4-benzoyloxy-6-methylcoumarin (4.0 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (12 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 140–50° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered and purified by the treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 155°. Yield 2 g. (Found: C, 72.66; H, 4.21. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.85; H, 4.32%).

K. R. Acetylation of 4-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-6-methylcoumarin: 4-Phenyl-9-methyl-2,5-dioxo-2H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran (I Ib): A mixture of 6-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-6-methylcoumarin (1.0 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.) was heated at 150–60° in an oil bath for 6 hrs. After the completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was poured into ice and water. The separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 233°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 74.81; H, 4.22. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99; H, 3.97%).

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran: Ethyl-3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylate (IVd): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-6-methylcoumarin (2.0 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (1.8 ml.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (4.0 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 25 hrs. After the evaporation of acetone the separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dil. alcohol, m.p. 193°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 72.08; H, 5.10. $C_{21}H_{16}O_5$ requires S, 72.40; H, 4.63%).

Hydrolysis: 3-Phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IVe): Ethyl-3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran, 2-carboxylate (0.5 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (5 ml.) and was refluxed with sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 10%) on a water bath for 45 mins. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and acidified. The separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 261°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 71.61; H, 4.13. $C_{19}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 71.25; H, 3.78%).

Decarboxylation: 3-Phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (IVf): A mixture of 3-phenyl-8-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (0.3 g.), copper bronze (0.2 g.) and quinoline (5 ml.) was heated on a sand bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and allowed to cool. It was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and the separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 198°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 78.14; H, 4.50. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.25; H, 4.38%).

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